

RESPOND

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Reception Policies, Practices and Responses

Italy Country Report

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List of abbreviations

AIDA: Asylum Information Database

ANCI: *Associazione Nazionale Comuni Italiani* (National Association of Italian Municipalities)

ASGI: *Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione* (Association for Legal Studies on Immigration)

CARA: *Centri di Accoglienza per Richiedenti Asilo* (Reception Centers for Asylum Seekers)

CAS: *Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria* (Extraordinary Reception Centers)

CDA: *Centri di Accoglienza* (Reception Centers)

CPRs: *Centri di Permanenza per i Rimpatri* (Detention Centers for Repatriation)

CPSA: *Centri di Primo Soccorso e Accoglienza* (First Aid and Reception Centers)

EASO: European Asylum Support Office

EU: European Union

IOM: International Organization for Migration

MEI: Meso-level Interview

MII: Micro-level Interview

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization

SIM: *Sistema Informativo Minori* (Minors Information System)

SIPROIMI: *Sistema di Protezione per Titolari di Protezione Internazionale e Minori Stranieri non Accompagnati* (System of Protection for Beneficiaries of International Protection and Unaccompanied Minors)

SOPs: Standard Operating Procedures

SPRAR: *Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati* (National System for the Protection for Asylum Seekers and Refugees)

UNHCR: United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees

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About the project

RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond is a comprehensive study of responses to the 2015 Refugee Crisis. One of the most visible impacts of the refugee crisis is the polarization of politics in EU Member States and intra-Member State policy incoherence in responding to the crisis. Incoherence stems from diverse constitutional structures, legal provisions, economic conditions, public policies and cultural norms. More research is needed to determine how to mitigate conflicting needs and objectives. With the goal of enhancing the governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU), its Member States and neighbors, RESPOND brings together fourteen partners from eleven countries and several different disciplines. In particular, the project aims to:

- provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research;
- critically analyze governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

The countries selected for the study are Austria, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. By focusing on these countries, RESPOND studies migration governance along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. These fields literally represent refugees' journeys across borders, from their confrontations with protection policies, to their travels through reception centers, and in some cases, ending with their integration into new societies.

To explore all of these dimensions, RESPOND employs a truly interdisciplinary approach, using legal and political analysis, comparative historical analysis, political claims analysis, socio-economic and cultural analysis, longitudinal survey analysis, interview based analysis, and photo voice techniques (some of these methods are implemented later in the project). The research is innovatively designed as multi-level because research on migration governance now operates beyond macro level actors, such as states or the EU. Migration management engages meso and micro level actors as well. Local governments, NGOs, associations and refugees are not merely the passive recipients of policies, but are shaping policies from the ground-up.

The project also focuses on learning from refugees. RESPOND defines a new subject position for refugees, as people who have been forced to find creative solutions to life threatening situations and as people who can generate new forms of knowledge and information as a result.

Executive summary

This report explores the development of the Italian reception regime between 2011 and 2018. The aim is to study the legal and policy framework, to map the institutions and actors involved in implementation, and to assess policy coherence with respect to international and EU standards.

The report firstly traces the evolution of legal provisions and policies and describes in details the functioning of the multi-level system of reception, that is organized into the three main phases: first aid and assistance, first reception, and second reception. Secondly, the main issues at stake are reported, and the discrepancy between norms and practices – as well coordination problems between diverse actors at different levels of government – are scrutinized. In particular, specific problems concerned with housing, access to labor market and education, services and allowances, and reception of vulnerable groups are analyzed.

In formulating policy recommendations, the report mainly concludes that Italy should improve coordination in multi-level governance and strengthen cooperation between civil society associations and institutional actors. Decision making and administrative procedures should be speeded up. This is deemed to be crucial in order to guarantee immediate access to material reception conditions, as well as to health services, housing, labour market, and education system. Finally, a system to monitor and verify the performance of the bodies managing reception centers should be set up, and measures to guarantee territorial uniformity in access to material reception conditions throughout the country should be taken.

1. Introduction

This report focuses on reception policies and practices in Italy between 2011 and 2018. Its overall aim is to study the legal and policy framework in the area of reception, to map the institutions and actors involved in implementation, and to assess policy coherence with respect to international and EU standards. The term 'reception' refers to the ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions, and actors that are concerned with the time period between migrants' arrival on Italian soil and the decision about the asylum application.

Italy represents one of the EU external borders¹ and, given its geographical position, analyzing its domestic legal and policy measures is vital to the understanding of the overall EU strategy in the field of reception – above all for what the Mediterranean border is concerned. In the last two decades, the first real watershed in terms of migration flows through the Mediterranean is 2011 with 62.692 non-EU arrivals. Following this first peak, migration flows have decreased in 2012, and then increased again to reach a second peak in 2014 (170.100 arrivals). A third peak was reached in 2016, when 181.436 non-EU nationals landed on Italian shores. However, since 2017 flows have been decreasing again. In 2018, the number dropped to 23.370 (-80,42% with respect to 2017 and -87.12 % with respect to 2016). Most migrants who reached Italy departed from Libya (90% in 2016)² (UNHCR 2017).

Table 1. Arrivals of non-EU nationals by sea

	Total
2011	62.692
2012	13.267
2013	42.925
2014	170.100
2015	153.842
2016	181.436
2017	119.310
2018	23.370

Source: Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration - Ministry of the Interior (2018); Pannia, Federico, and D'Amato (2018)

Note: Data refer to 31st of December of each year

¹ Overall, the Schengen area extends along around 44 000 km of external sea borders.

² The decrease in arrivals has been mostly due to bilateral agreements signed between Italy and North African countries. These agreements are part of the Italian externalization strategy that will be analyzed in the remainder of the article.

After presenting the main sources of evidence and the methods adopted, section 3 reviews the formal legal and policy framework concerning the Italian reception system, tracking the evolution of national as well as EU framework legislation. This part describes in details the functioning of the three main phases that characterize the reception system: first aid and assistance, first reception, and second reception. The section highlights the multi-level character of the system, involving different actors at the national, regional, and municipal level. Moreover, norms regulating the reception of vulnerable groups are also discussed.

In section 4, the national reception regime is scrutinized. This part of the report highlights the main issues at stake, stressing the discrepancy between norms and practices and the coordination problems between diverse actors at different levels of government. The section is again structured around the three main phases of first aid and assistance, first reception, and second reception. In particular, problems relating to housing, early access to labor market and education, services and allowances, and reception of vulnerable groups are discussed. Finally, section 5 concludes summarizing the main findings and providing policy recommendations.

2. Methodology and sources

Empirical evidence provided in this report is mainly drawn from national, international and EU legislation, official government documents, policy reports by both governmental and non-governmental institutions, secondary sources, academic literature, and 44 semi-structured interviews to meso- and micro-level actors.

As for the meso level, 15 interviews were conducted between May 2018 and January 2019. Interviewees were selected through snowball sampling, where the starting point was relevant experts and informants in the field of migration. Selected interviewees included legal experts, activists, migration experts from universities and research institutes, NGO office managers, social workers, officials and decision-makers. Interview questions were open ended, adjusted to the interviewees' profile, and covered several aspects of the reception system in Italy, as well as aspects related to border management, refugee protection, and integration practices.

As regards micro-level interviews, 29 semi-structured interviews were conducted between May 2018 and April 2019. The relevant migration flows in the Italian case are essentially determined by the country's geographical position in the Mediterranean. More specifically, Italy is mostly impacted by migration flows from Sub-Saharan African countries. Accordingly, the sample of interviewees mainly encompasses asylum seekers, refugees, and migrants from this region who came to Italy through the Central Mediterranean route (n=25).

Figure 1. Micro-level interviewees: Route

Source: Author's elaboration

In particular, the interviewees' countries of origin include Nigeria (n=10), Gambia (n=5), Ghana (n=3), Ivory Coast (n=2), Sierra Leone (n=1), Cameroon (n=1), Mali (n=1), Liberia (n=1) and Senegal (n=1). The sample also includes two interviewees from North African countries (Morocco and Libya), and two interviewees from Pakistan and El Salvador. With respect to legal statuses, 3 out of 29 interviewees had not applied for asylum at the moment of the interview and were therefore classified as economic migrants. The majority of the interviewees were asylum seekers. Participants' ages ranged from 18 to 37 and they had arrived in Italy

between 2011 and 2018³. One of the main limitations regarding micro-level interviews is constituted by the fact that almost all of the interviews (26 out of 29) were conducted in reception centers.⁴ This might have affected the interviewees' responses. Figure 2 matches the micro-level interviewees' countries of origin against their legal statuses.

Figure 2. Micro-level interviewees: Country of origin and legal status

Source: Author's elaboration

Interview transcripts were analyzed using NVivo, a qualitative data analysis software that helps to structure, organize, manage and query a large amount of data. Through qualitative content analysis, the material was systematically interpreted and described, and all the meanings in the text data that were relevant to the analysis were translated into categories of a coding scheme. In particular, the main categories of the coding scheme, namely, the key aspects on which the analysis was focused, were the key actors, problems, and solutions related to the reception regime in Italy.

³ Only 1 interviewee (economic migrant) arrived in Italy in 2001.

⁴ 22 in Extraordinary Reception Centres (*Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria, CAS*) and 4 in reception facilities of the National System for the Protection for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (*Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati, SPRAR*)

3. Overview of the multi-level legal and policy framework

Directive 2013/33/EU⁵ laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection applies to all third-country nationals or stateless individuals who have made an application for international protection in respect of which a final decision has not yet been taken (Art. 2(b)). As defined by the Directive, the term reception refers to all those conditions and measures that Member States grant to applicants for international protection. In particular, material reception conditions are all those measures concerned with 'housing, food and clothing provided in kind, or as financial allowances or in vouchers, or a combination of the three, and a daily expenses allowance' (Art. 2(g)).

Italy transposed and implemented the European Directive with Legislative Decree No. 142/2015⁶. As specified in the Decree, the reception applies to applicants from the moment of the expression of the willingness to seek international protection (Art. 1(2)). In compliance with the European directive, the office that receives the applications informs the applicant about the reception conditions within a reasonable time not exceeding 15 days after they have lodged their application for international protection (Art. 3). Moreover, the applicant is issued with a residence permit for the purpose of applying for asylum. The document is valid for six months and it is renewable until the decision on the application is taken.

The Italian reception system has somehow developed according to the model envisaged by the UNCHR in the early 2000s that pointed to the need to establish a complementarity between 'first' and 'second' reception (UNHCR 2000, 2001; see also Campesi 2018; EASO 2016;). As for first reception, facilities run by the central government were seen as the best response to the needs of asylum seekers upon their arrival. Services should include health and psychological assistance as well as legal counselling that should properly channel asylum seekers through the asylum procedure: "the underlying idea was to concentrate the provision of these services in a limited number of large reception facilities, while ensuring a rapid turnover inside them" (Campesi 2018: 493). Instead, it was thought that NGOs would have better run second reception activities in that "the accommodation in small facilities or apartments is more functional to the needs of those who often remain for long periods of time awaiting the outcome of their asylum request" (2018: 493).

Accordingly, as established by Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 (Art. 8(1)), the Italian reception system is based on a 'loyal' cooperation between different levels of government: national, regional, and municipal. As provided by the Consolidated Law on Immigration⁷, regions and local municipalities are entrusted to play an essential role in the governance of migration, in close collaboration with the central government. In particular, subnational

⁵ Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast).

⁶ Legislative Decree No 142 of 18 August 2015, "*Attuazione della direttiva 2013/33/UE recante norme relative all'accoglienza dei richiedenti protezione internazionale, nonché della direttiva 2013/32/UE, recante procedure comuni ai fini del riconoscimento e della revoca dello status di protezione internazionale.*" This Decree has repealed the previous Legislative Decree No 140 of 30 May 2005 implementing the Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers. However, the reception system has remained substantially the same (see also AIDA 2015).

⁷ Legislative Decree No 286 of 25 July 1998, "*Testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero.*"

governments have to play a crucial role in a number of domains, such as education (Art. 38) and social integration (Art. 42). Subnational governments should remove any obstacles to the full recognition of foreigners' legal entitlements provided at the national level, with specific reference to housing, health care, education, social assistance and social integration (Pannia, Federico, and D'Amato 2018)

In 2014, an agreement between the central government, the regions, and the municipalities made operational the integrated action of the various levels of government in the field of reception, and approved the first National Plan to deal with the extraordinary flow of non-EU citizens (Presidency of the Council of Ministers 2014). As highlighted by the Ministry of the Interior (2015a: 23), "the basic aspect on which the implementation of the Plan is focused is the gradual overcoming of the emergency-based approach that has characterized the Italian reception system until now". Central to the agreement is the recognition of the need to implement a single multi-level system of reception – that also includes the participation of NGOs – divided into three phases: *a*) first aid and assistance, *b*) first reception, and *c*) second reception⁸ (AIDA 2017, 2018; Campesi 2018; Chamber of Deputies 2017; Federico and Pannia 2018; Ministry of the Interior 2015a, 2016; Pannia, Federico, and D'Amato 2018; Presidency of the Council of Ministers 2014).

Planning and coordination of reception activities are undertaken by the National and Regional Coordination Boards (Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, Art. 9(1)). In particular, the National Coordination Board (*Tavolo di Coordinamento Nazionale*) at the Department of Civil Liberties of the Ministry of the Interior identifies the guidelines and plans the interventions aimed at optimizing the reception system, including the criteria for the regional distribution of the facilities to be allocated for reception purposes (Art. 16(1)). This Board represents 'the landmark of the governance of the national reception system, where national and European planning come together' (Presidency of the Council of Ministers 2014: 14). Moreover, on the basis of the number of asylum seekers that are expected to be received, the Board prepares annually a National Plan for Reception that identifies the needs of the facilities to be allocated for reception purposes (Art. 16(2)). The guidelines and the National Plan are implemented at the subnational level through the Regional Coordination Boards (*Tavoli di Coordinamento Regionale*) established at the Prefectures⁹ (*Prefecture*), which identify the criteria for the distribution within the Region of the structures to be allocated for reception purposes (Art. 16(3)). Control and monitoring of the management of first and second reception facilities are conducted by The Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration – also through the Prefectures (Art. 20(1)).

3.1 First aid and assistance¹⁰

During this phase, activities related to identification (including identification of vulnerable households or persons), provision of necessary material need (e.g., hygiene, clothing), health screening, and provision of information are carried out (Presidency of the Council of Ministers 2014). Operations take place in governmental facilities set up in the principal places of disembarkation (Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, Art. 8(2)). First Aid and Reception Centers

⁸ The phases of first aid and assistance and first reception together correspond to 'first reception' in EASO and UNCHR understanding.

⁹ Prefectures are local offices (provincial level), of the Ministry of the Interior.

¹⁰ Extracts from Terlizzi (2019).

(*Centri di Primo Soccorso e Accoglienza, CPSA*) were created in 2006¹¹ for the purposes of first aid and identification before asylum seekers are transferred to other centers. These centers are now formally operating as “hotspots”¹².

In 2015, at the peak of the European migration crisis, the European Commission presented the so-called ‘hotspot approach’ as part of the European Agenda on Migration¹³. The hotspots are facilities for initial reception, identification, registration and fingerprinting of migrants arriving in the EU by sea. The approach aims at providing assistance to countries with high migratory pressure and at coordinating the activities of EU institutions (EASO, Frontex, Europol, and Eurojust) and national authorities at the external borders of the EU.

In implementing the European Agenda on Migration, in September 2015 the Ministry of the Interior has drafted a document titled ‘Italian Roadmap’¹⁴. In compliance with the 2015 Proposal for a Council Decision establishing provisional measures in the area of international protection for the benefit of Italy and Greece¹⁵, the document includes those measures aimed at improving “the capacity, quality and efficiency of the Italian asylum system in the areas of first reception and repatriation” (Ministry of the Interior 2015: 2). The roadmap also complies with Legislative Decree No 142/2015 implementing Directive 2013/32/EU¹⁶ and Directive 2013/33/EU.

Currently, there are five hotspots on the Italian territory (in Lampedusa, Messina, Pozzallo, Taranto and Trapani). The Ministry of Interior has issued a document containing the Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) applicable to the Italian hotspots. As defined in the document, a hotspot is a “designated area, usually (but not necessarily) in the proximity of a landing place where, as soon as possible and consistent with the Italian regulatory framework, new arrivals land safely and are subjected to medical screenings, receive a leaflet on legislation concerning immigration and asylum, they are controlled, pre-identified, and, after having being informed about their current condition as irregular immigrants and the possibility to apply for international protection, they are fingerprinted. Subsequently, they receive detailed information on the procedure of international protection, the relocation programme and the assisted voluntary return” (Ministry of the Interior, n.d.: 4). The document also lists the basic staffing required for each hotspot: medical staff; Frontex team to provide support for pre-identification and screening activities; EASO experts to provide information on the relocation programme; Frontex expert for the verification of documents; forensic experts for the acquisition of fingerprints.

¹¹ Law No 563 of 29 December 1995, “*Conversione in legge del decreto-legge 30 ottobre 1995, n. 451, recante disposizioni urgenti per l’ulteriore impiego del personale delle Forze armate in attivita’ di controllo della frontiera marittima nella regione Puglia*”.

¹² Legislative Decree No 13 of 17 February 2017, “*Disposizioni urgenti per l’accelerazione dei procedimenti in materia di protezione internazionale, nonché per il contrasto dell’immigrazione illegale*”.

¹³ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions: A European Agenda on Migration’ (COM(2015) 240 final).

¹⁴ The document had the task of clarifying the organizational flow that must lead from the reception and identification of migrants disembarked to their possible inclusion in the relocation mechanism. The Roadmap contains detailed information about the implementation of the hotspot approach by Italian authorities.

¹⁵ COM(2015) 286 final. 2015/125 (NLE).

¹⁶ Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection.

The hotspot approach has been conceived as holistic and therefore involves several and parallel activities carried out by a multitude of actors. The key players and stakeholders involved in the operation of Italian hotspots are as follows (Ministry of the Interior n.d.):

- Medical triage activities on board or upon arrival: medical personnel on board, land-based medical personnel. UNHCR and IOM support national authorities for identification of persons with specific needs.
- Identification through photos before or immediately after landing: National Police, health personnel.
- Transfer to hotspots locations: National Police, Carabinieri Corps, Financial Guard, Prefecture.
- Personal security checks on entry into the Hotspot: National Police, Financial Guard, Navy, Coast Guard, EUNAVFOR Med¹⁷, Frontex.
- Registration and security checks: National Police, Frontex, cultural mediators.
- Documents checks: National Police, Frontex.
- Information activities on the current legislation on immigration and international protection procedure: UNHCR, IOM.
- Fingerprints verification and checks in national, European and international police data banks: National Police.
- Identification of potential unaccompanied foreign minors: National Police and medical personnel.
- Information campaign on relocation: EASO, UNHCR, cultural mediators.
- Specific provision for unaccompanied minors (UASC) and other persons with specific needs: Municipalities and Prefectures, National Police, EASO, UNHCR, cultural mediators.
- Transfers to reception centers, reception centers dedicated to relocation or pre-removal facilities: Ministry of the Interior – Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration, EASO, National Police.

Figures 3 and 4 show the capacity of the five Italian hotspots and the presence of EU personnel.

¹⁷ European Union Naval Force Mediterranean – Operation Sophia (see <https://www.operationsophia.eu/>).

Figure 3. Hotspot state of play

HOTSPOTS IN ITALY ⁱ					
	LAMPEDUSA	POZZALLO	TARANTO	TRAPANI	MESSINA
Total Reception Capacity	500	300	400	400	
EU Presence	European Border and Coast Guard: 13 experts	European Border and Coast Guard: 13 experts	European Border and Coast Guard: 6 experts	European Border and Coast Guard: 12 experts	
	EASO: 1 Member State Expert	EASO: 1 Member State Expert	EASO: 1 Member State Expert	EASO: 1 Member State Expert	
	EASO: 2 cultural mediators	EASO: 3 cultural mediators	EASO: 2 cultural mediators	EASO: 6 cultural mediators	EASO: 2 cultural mediators

Source: Policy Department for Citizens' Rights and Constitutional Affairs (2018)

Note: The hotspot in Messina has a capacity of 250 places.

Figure 4. Start of operation and capacity of hotspots in Italy

	Start of operation	Total reception capacity
Taranto	February 2016	400 Temporarily closed in March 2018
Trapani	December 2015	400
Messina	September 2017	250
Pozzallo	January 2016	300
Lampedusa	October 2015	500 Limited activities since March 2018
Total capacity		1 850

Source: European Parliamentary Research Service (2018)

3.2 First reception

First reception is provided to those individuals who have expressed a willingness to seek international protection. Activities take place in collective centers or in facilities to be established by Ministerial Decree. These include facilities previously known as Reception Centers for Asylum Seekers (*Centri di Accoglienza per Richiedenti Asilo*, CARA) and Reception Centers (*Centri di Accoglienza*, CDA). In first reception centers operations related to the legal position of the foreigner are carried out (Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, Art. 9 and Art. 10). The applicant is allowed to leave the facility during the daytime with the obligation to return at night. For relevant personal reasons or for reasons relating to the examination of the application, the applicant may ask the Prefect for a temporary permit to leave the center for a period of time different from or longer than the standard period (Art. 10(2)).

First reception facilities offer basic services to asylum seekers compared to those provided by second reception centers (see below). These services include food, accommodation, clothing, basic information/legal services (AIDA 2015). As specified by Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, these facilities 'shall ensure the respect for privacy (including gender differences), age-related needs, protection of the physical and mental health, family unity, and the provision of the necessary measures for persons with special needs. [Moreover], appropriate measures shall be taken to prevent all forms of violence and to ensure the safety and protection of applicants' (Art. 10(1)).

In the event of substantial arrivals or if no places are available in first as well as in second reception facilities, the asylum seeker should be temporarily accommodated in Extraordinary Reception Center (*Centri di Accoglienza Straordinaria*, CAS) identified and activated by the Prefecture (Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, Art. 11).

3.3 Second reception

When first reception operations are concluded, asylum seekers who do not have sufficient financial resources (Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, Art. 14(3))¹⁸ should be transferred to second-line reception centers which are managed by the municipalities within the National System of Protection for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (*Sistema di Protezione per Richiedenti Asilo e Rifugiati*, SPRAR), with the financial support of the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services (Art. 14(1)). The SPRAR was established by Law No 189/2002¹⁹ as a publicly funded network of local authorities and third sector organizations which accommodates asylum seekers, refugees and other beneficiaries of international protection. As defined by a circular of the Ministry of the Interior²⁰, the SPRAR constitutes a *partnership* between the central government and the subnational governments (regions and municipalities). In contrast to governmental first-line reception facilities, the SPRAR consists of small reception facilities where assistance and integration services are provided on the basis of small-scale decentralized projects (AIDA 2015, 2016). The SPRAR system

¹⁸ Prefectures are competent to assess the insufficiency of migrants' financial resources on the basis of the annual social allowance (€ 5.889,00).

¹⁹ Law No 189 of 30 July 2002, "*Modifica alla normativa in materia di immigrazione e di asilo*".

²⁰ Circular of the Ministry of the Interior of 11 October 2016, "*Regole per l'avvio di un sistema di ripartizione graduale e sostenibile dei richiedenti asilo e dei rifugiati sul territorio nazionale attraverso lo SPRAR*".

constitutes the evolution of the project “*Azione Comune*” (Common Action)²¹ established in 1999 with the aim of responding to the Kosovo emergency through the creation of a network of territorial services for the reception of asylum seekers²². The objective was to promote a model of reception that would favor small and medium-sized reception centers aiming at integrating asylum seekers into Italian society (Chamber of Deputies 2017).

In 2016, the Ministry of the Interior issued a Decree²³ specifying how municipalities could access funding from the National Fund for Asylum Policies and Services. The Decree also approved the guidelines for the functioning of the SPRAR system. As for access to funding, Article 2 states that municipalities have to submit an application containing the (three-year) project proposals relating to the activation of reception services to the Department for Civil Liberties and Immigration of the Ministry of the Interior. As for the SPRAR guidelines, Article 21 specifies that, for the implementation of the reception services, municipalities may make use of ‘implementing bodies’ (third sector organizations) which must have experience in the reception of applicants and/or holders of international protection. As provided by the Ministerial Decree, ‘the main objective of the SPRAR reception services is to (re)gain the individual autonomy of the applicants/holders of international protection’ (Art 29(1)). To this aim, it is deemed essential ‘to place the applicants at the center of the Protection System, making them active protagonists of their own path of reception and integration’, instead of considering them as mere passive beneficiaries of reception measures (Art. 29(2)). Crucial to this approach is the concept of *empowerment*, which is understood as a process ‘through which individuals can reconstruct their capacity for choice and planning and regain their perception of their own value, potential and opportunities’ (SPRAR 2018: 7). That is why the SPRAR system provides *integrated reception*, which consists in ‘the implementation of basic material measures (food and lodging), together with services aimed at supporting paths of social inclusion’ (Art. 30(1)). This implies that the basic material interventions are contextual to services aimed at acquiring autonomy (SPRAR 2018). Specifically, integrated reception consists of the following services, which are considered ‘guaranteed and mandatory minimum services’ (*servizi minimi garantiti obbligatori*) (Artt. 30(2) and 31; see also SPRAR 2017b, 2017a):

- *Linguistic and cultural mediation*. Local authorities must guarantee linguistic and cultural mediation in order to facilitate relationships and communication between the individual beneficiaries, the reception project and the territorial context.
- *Material reception*. Local authorities must guarantee food and meet the demands of the beneficiaries so as to respect their cultural and religious traditions. Moreover, local authorities have to provide sufficient quantities of clothing, personal hygiene products according to the individual needs, and pocket money.
- *Orientation and access to local services*. Local authorities have an obligation to facilitate access to local minimum services and to guarantee the teaching of Italian language and schooling for children.

²¹ In Italian, *comune* means municipality.

²² The 1990s have witnessed massive inflows of migrants related to the Albanian crises of 1991 and 1997, the civil war in Somalia of 1992 and the exodus from the former Yugoslavia.

²³ Ministerial Decree of 10 August 2016, “*Modalità di accesso da parte degli enti locali ai finanziamenti del Fondo nazionale per le politiche ed i servizi dell’asilo per la predisposizione dei servizi di accoglienza per i richiedenti e i beneficiari di protezione internazionale e per i titolari del permesso umanitario, nonché approvazione delle linee guida per il funzionamento del Sistema di protezione per richiedenti asilo e rifugiati (SPRAR)*”.

- *Vocational training.* Local authorities must design policy instruments aimed at enhancing the value of individual backgrounds taking into account the expectations of the beneficiaries (curriculum vitae, skills assessment and certification, etc.). Moreover, they have to assist the beneficiaries in vocational training in order to encourage the acquisition of new skills. Local authorities also have to facilitate the procedures for the recognition of academic and professional qualifications and access to university education.
- *Job assistance.* Local authorities must provide information on Italian labour legislation and employment services available in the territory, as well as support for job placement, while guaranteeing the beneficiaries' individual characteristics or conditions of vulnerability.
- *Housing assistance.* Local authorities must ensure that information on the relevant Italian legislation is provided. They also must promote access to public housing, as well as to the private housing market through promotional actions, support and intermediation between beneficiaries and landlords/owners. These activities must take into account the beneficiaries' individual characteristics or conditions of vulnerability.
- *Assistance in social integration.* Local authorities must promote the implementation of awareness-raising activities and information with a view to facilitating dialogue between beneficiaries and the local community. They also have to build and consolidate the territorial support network involving all the local actors participating in the project, promoting the participation of beneficiaries in the associative and public life of the territory.
- *Legal assistance.* Local authorities must guarantee legal guidance on the Italian and European legislation on asylum, as well as ensure assistance in the interlocutory process with the institutional actors in charge of the different phases of the procedure for granting international protection.
- *Psycho-social and health protection.* Local authorities are obliged to ensure the activation of psycho-social support based on the specific needs of individual beneficiaries. To this aim they must build and consolidate the collaboration with the all public and private actors who can participate in the support, rehabilitation and care of beneficiaries with specific social and health needs.

Applicants have the right to stay in the SPRAR system until the Territorial Commission notifies them about the decision on the asylum application. From the moment of notification of the granting of international protection, the applicant can stay in SPRAR facilities for a further six months (Art. 35). An extension can be granted for extraordinary circumstances (Art. 36).

As for the withdrawal of reception conditions, according to Article 23(1) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 the Prefect may decide on an individual basis to revoke material reception conditions on the following grounds: (a) the asylum seeker did not present him or herself at the assigned center or left the center without notifying Prefecture; (b) the asylum seeker did not present him or herself before the competent authorities for the personal interview even though he or she was notified thereof; (c) the asylum seeker has previously lodged an asylum application in Italy; (d) the authorities decide that the asylum seeker possesses sufficient financial resources; or (e) the asylum seeker has committed a serious

violation or continuous violation of the accommodation center's internal rules or the asylum seeker's conduct was considered seriously violent. Against the decision of withdrawal of material reception conditions, according to Article 23(5), asylum seekers have the right to lodge an appeal before the Regional Administrative Court (*Tribunale Amministrativo Regionale*), and they can benefit from free legal assistance (AIDA 2018).

Recently, Decree Law 113/2018 implemented by Law 132/2018, has brought about significant changes to second reception and, as a consequence, to the whole Italian reception system. First of all, the reception paths of asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection are separated (AIDA 2018). Indeed, the Decree prevents asylum seekers from accessing the SPRAR system, which was renamed System of Protection for Beneficiaries of International Protection and Unaccompanied Minors (*Sistema di Protezione per Titolari di Protezione Internazionale e Minori Stranieri non Accompagnati*, SIPROIMI). Therefore, asylum seekers can now be accommodated only in first reception centers and in CAS²⁴. Only beneficiaries of international protection and unaccompanied minors can access the SIPROIMI. Victims of trafficking, domestic violence, and persons holding a residence permit for medical treatment – due to a natural calamity in the country of origin – or for acts of particular civic value can also access the SIPROIMI system (AIDA 2018). *De facto*, the Decree has abolished the phase of second reception.

3.4 Reception of vulnerable groups

Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 provides that accommodation has to take into account “the specific needs of vulnerable persons, such as minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled persons, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, victims of human trafficking, persons suffering from serious illness or mental disorders, victims of genital mutilation, persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, as well as victims of violence related to sexual orientation or gender identity” (Art. 17(1)).

Unaccompanied foreign minors

As for unaccompanied foreign minors – who on the basis of national and international law cannot be subject to expulsion – Law No 47/2018²⁵ defines them as minors who are for any reason present in the Italian territory without assistance and representation from parents or other adults legally responsible for him or her according to the laws in force in the Italian legal system (Art. 2 (1)). Moreover, Article 1 states that unaccompanied foreign minors are entitled to the same rights of protection as minors of Italian or EU citizenship. This is in compliance with the 1989 United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child²⁶, stating that “states shall respect and ensure the rights set forth in the present Convention to each child within their jurisdiction without discrimination of any kind, irrespective of the child's or his or her parent's or legal guardian's race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national, ethnic or

²⁴ Those asylum seekers already present in SPRAR facilities before the approval of the Decree are allowed to stay in those facilities until the end of their asylum procedure.

²⁵ Law No 47 of 7 April 2017, “*Disposizioni in materia di misure di protezione dei minori stranieri non accompagnati*”.

²⁶ The United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly resolution 44/25 of 20 November 1989, entered into force on 2 September 1990.

social origin, property, disability, birth or other status. [Moreover, States] shall take all appropriate measures to ensure that the child is protected against all forms of discrimination or punishment on the basis of the status, activities, expressed opinions, or beliefs of the child's parents, legal guardians, or family members" (Art. 2).

The general legislation on family placement applies to unaccompanied foreign minors as well. It provides that the child temporarily deprived of a suitable family environment is entrusted to a family, preferably with minor children, or to a single person, able to ensure the maintenance and education of the minor. Where an appropriate family placement is not possible, the minor can be received in reception facilities (Law No 184/1983, Art. 2)²⁷. According to Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, unaccompanied foreign minors cannot be received in reception centers for adults and should be received in governmental facilities for the first reception of minors (Art. 19) (even in CAS for minors). These facilities – activated through the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund²⁸ – provide first aid and assistance, and procedures for the identification and age assessment are carried out. Moreover, qualified personnel are required to have an interview with the minor, aimed at deepening his or her personal and family history and at bringing out any other element useful for his or her protection. These activities have to be undertaken together with a cultural mediator and assisted, where possible, by organizations with proven and specific experience in the protection of minors.

Recently, with the establishment of the SIPROIMI, it has started a gradual transfer to SIPROIMI facilities of all the minors who are present in governmental facilities for first reception. SIPROIMI facilities are required to provide a series of services aimed at supporting social inclusion and must take into account the specific needs of unaccompanied foreign minors such as: linguistic and cultural mediation; teaching of the Italian language and integration into school and professional training; guidance and accompaniment to employment, housing and social integration; access to services in the territory; orientation and legal assistance; psycho-social and health protection; the provision of pocket money (SIPROIMI n.d.).

Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 and Prime Ministerial Decree No 535/1999²⁹, as well as the 2014 agreement between the central government, the regions, and the municipalities (Presidency of the Council of Ministers 2014), provides that the Directorate General for Immigration and Integration Policies of the Ministry of Labour and Social Policies is responsible for monitoring the presence of unaccompanied minors throughout the country. In order to carry out this task, the Directorate has developed the Minors Information System (*Sistema Informativo Minori*, SIM). The SIM also allows to track minors' movements on the national territory and to manage the data relating to their status and placement.

²⁷ Law No 184 of 4 May 1983, "*Disciplina dell'adozione e dell'affidamento dei minori*".

²⁸ The Fund was established by Regulation (EU) No 516/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014.

²⁹ Prime Ministerial Decree of 9 December 1999, "*Regolamento concernente i compiti del Comitato per i minori stranieri, a norma dell'articolo 33, commi 2 e 2-bis, del decreto legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286*".

4. Practices of reception: Key actors and problems

While the previous section has described the formal legal and policy framework concerning reception, this section focuses on how the Italian reception regime functions in practice, highlighting the discrepancy between norms and practice and the key issues that have been arising over time.

What emerges from the meso-level interviews is that the actors that are deemed to be crucial in the multi-level governance of the Italian reception system are: a) Central government (Ministry of the Interior and Ministry of Labor and Social Policies); b) Municipalities, together with the National Association of Italian Municipalities (*Associazione Nazionale Comuni Italiani*, ANCI); and c) Third sector organizations.

Figure 5. Main actors in the Italian reception regime

Source: Author's elaboration

As for the regional level, though the Constitution exclusively reserves the competence over immigration and asylum for the central government, it also provides that the regions exercise concurrent legislative powers in a number of areas which are relevant for reception policy, such as education and health care. However, according to some meso-level interviewees, though the regional level should formally have some powers, in practice it does not have much responsibility:

“the regional level is completely missing. There is a ministerial level that communicates directly with the municipalities. [...] Regional governance is completely exempted. [...] ‘Dialogue’ is between Prefectures and mayors. [...] The region would be the natural interlocutor” (MEI no. 4); *“regional authorities are bypassed”* (MEI no 13). As a social worker has commented, *“unfortunately, the fundamental actor is the Minister of the Interior through the Prefectures: the reception [of asylum seekers and refugees] is seen as a problem of public order”* (MEI no. 7).

Most of the interviewees agree that the crucial players in the reception system are non-governmental actors:

“I believe that, more than state actors, it is the civil society associations that make specific and important choices for migrants” (MEI no. 14). As a legal expert has reported, *“non-state actors operating at the local level are those who in practice have 90% influence on the reception system”* (MEI no. 1).

In fact, starting from 2014 in particular, there has been a proliferation of civil society organizations dealing with asylum seekers and refugees in the field of first and second reception. This is reflected by the increasing number of cooperatives that activated ad-hoc programs often responding to public calls and tenders to manage the reception of asylum seekers and refugees in first reception, CAS, and SPRAR facilities. Services provided by civil society organizations include cultural mediation, language courses, identification of skills, voluntary work, vocational training, and internships (Maggini and Collini 2019). According to an activist for an intercultural association,

“it seems that it is mainly small NGOs and the volunteers that have taken care of the whole management of the emergency from 2015 up until now. [...] In my opinion they [civil society organizations] are the main actors of the reception system, with all the risks that this may entail” (MEI no. 2). As stated by a migration expert, *“advocacy associations for the protection of human rights – as well as the voluntary sector – are everything to the reception system [...] at European, national and local level”* (MEI no. 4).

Besides NGOs, it has been stressed that

“the role of religious associations in welcoming people has been crucial, above all when there are no places available in governmental reception centers. This is a factor to underline” (MEI no. 5).

A key issue that has been highlighted is that the whole system is regulated by a fragmentary legislative framework that is shaped by heterogeneous legislative decrees. This makes the reception of asylum seekers and refugees a very uncertain process (see also La Bella 2019). Moreover, according to a NGO office manager, the reception system is only formally based on a loyal cooperation between different levels of government:

“I see the collaboration between subnational and national governments at a formal institutional level but not in practice. [In addition to that], collaboration between state and non-state actors is a bit unbalanced in the sense that non-state actors make up for a series of shortcomings of state actors (also at the local level) and therefore increasingly find themselves carrying out functions that should in reality be carried out by state actors” (MEI no 6). As also a social worker has commented, *“there is too much distance between levels of government, in particular between the local level and the European Union”* (MEI no. 14).

Table 1 summarizes the key actors and the main issues in the Italian reception regime which will be analyzed in the remainder of the report.

Table 2. Reception practices: Key actors and problems

Category	Subcategory
<i>Asylum seekers and refugees basic needs</i>	Clear information about the asylum procedure
	Health assistance and psychological support
	Job assistance
	Teaching of Italian
	Vocational training
<i>Key actors</i>	Central government
	Municipalities
	Non-governmental actors
<i>Problems</i>	Collaboration between state and non-state actors is not sufficient
	Discrepancy between norms and practice
	Lack of financial resources
	Lack of psychological support
	No possibility for asylum seekers to choose the place of residence
	Reception conceived as an emergency measure
	Territorial differences in reception practices

Source: Author's elaboration

4.1 First aid and assistance³⁰

As for the operation of hotspots, what is important to highlight is that, besides the 'Italian Roadmap' and the SOPs, hotspots lack a solid legal basis. The activities taking place within hotspots are not regulated by any EU directive or regulation nor by Italian legislation. Vague reference to hotspots is provided only in Legislative Decree No 13/2017 (Pannia, Federico, and D'Amato 2018; see also Oxfam 2016).

Despite the absence of a clear legal framework regulating hotspots, the latter have become crucial within the Italian asylum system and the relocation procedure. However, several issues have been reported by non-governmental actors. For example, the Association for Legal Studies on Immigration (*Associazione per gli Studi Giuridici sull'Immigrazione*, ASGI) highlighted that hotspots have become part of "a standard procedure [according to which]

³⁰ Extracts from Terlizzi (2019).

migrants are detained without any court order, forced to be fingerprinted, and classified as asylum seekers or economic migrants depending on a summary assessment, mainly carried out either by using questionnaires filled in by migrants at disembarkation, or by orally asking questions relating to the reason why they have come to Italy” (AIDA 2017: 25; see also Extraordinary Commission for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights 2017; MEI no. 8). There are therefore several concerns about the actual understanding of the whole process by migrants (Extraordinary Commission for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights 2017). In many occasions, migrants are classified as economic migrants on nationality grounds only (MEI no. 5) (mainly those from Nigeria, Gambia, Senegal, Morocco, Algerian and Tunisia) and are notified with an expulsion order and detained in pre-removal facilities (Detention Centers for Repatriation, *Centri di Permanenza per i Rimpatri*, CPRs). Poor living conditions and severe violations of fundamental rights in hotspots and CPRs have been reported by NGOs and international organizations (MEI no. 1; see also Amnesty International 2016, 2018; Oxfam 2016; Pannia, Federico, and D’Amato 2018).

In April 2018, the European Committee for the Prevention of Torture and Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (CPT) released a report to the Italian government on its visit to Italy in June 2017 aimed at examining the situation of foreign nationals deprived of their liberty in the hotspots and CPRs. As stated in the report, while living conditions were good at Pozzallo and Trapani and acceptable for short stays at Lampedusa, the occupancy levels in all three hotspots regularly exceeded the official capacity (CPT 2018). Moreover, “noting that several categories of foreign nationals may be prevented from leaving the hotspots, the CPT raises the issue of the legal basis for deprivation of liberty in these centers and related problems regarding the existence and operation of legal safeguards” (2018: 3). As for pre-removal facilities, “critical comments are made about the austere and carceral environment observed at Caltanissetta and Turin CPRs, marked by a strong emphasis on security. In the light of practices observed at these two CPRs regarding the segregation of detainees, the CPT recommends that clear rules be adopted to regulate the use of segregation units/cells in CPRs” (2018: 4).

Background on micro-level interviewees’ journey

Most of the asylum seekers and refugees we interviewed declared that they did not know what to expect from their landing on Italian shores. They did not have any kind of information, not even about the journey, that in most of the cases was unplanned:

“before leaving my country I had some contacts in Libya, but had no idea of the situation” (MII no. 12);

“a woman told me she would help me to come to Europe to work [...]. She just told me ‘we will use flights’. But there was no flight” (MII no. 22);

“It wasn’t planned for a long time. I just woke up in a date, I took a bus from Gambia to Senegal and so I took the journey” (MII no. 1).

Almost all the respondents came to Italy through Libya, where most of them had been detained or enslaved:

“it wasn’t a prison, they kept me together with other people to work, they used to beat me” (MII no. 6);

“I stayed in Libya for a year. We stayed a week at the border with Libya. We were 7 people, all coming from Algeria. There they took everything from us and asked us to

pay to move on. Then we worked to continue the journey. There we had all the problems because they locked us up in a camp, which is like a prison, for two months” (MII no. 29);

“I was kidnapped in Libya. I was with 6-7 people and we were working for this person. Then this person brought us to the coast to take the boat” (MII no. 16).

During the journey, almost all of the interviewees had to pay money at check-points in order to continue:

“I started facing the challenges immediately when I left my country. In Senegal, Niger... In order to cross the borders you have to pay money. If you don't have the money they tell you that they have to deport you. You have to pay the money to be free, to continue the journey” (MII no. 1);

“We were stopped in many check-points in Libya, at the border with Niger. We had to pay the military and the police. During the journey, if you don't have the money you go to jail. You have to pay for the trip” (MII no. 1);

“In Burkina Faso at every check-point they ask a lot of money, and if you don't pay they beat you, they have electric... They beat a lot of people there” (MII no. 4);

“I always had to pay! [to cross borders]” (MII no. 14);

“I regretted leaving Algeria [...]. Everything I earned in Algeria I lost in Libya because they took everything from me, even the phone. I didn't even know whether they were authorities or not” (MII no. 29).

Some interviewees got some information about the journey to Italy once they arrived in Libya: *“I was in prison with someone who knew about the journey” (MII no. 17).*

4.2 First and second reception

In this section, problems specifically related to housing, early access to labor market and education, services and allowances, and reception of vulnerable groups during the phases of first and second reception are discussed.

Housing

As highlighted by AIDA (2017, 2018), though formally asylum seekers have the right to material reception conditions immediately after claiming asylum, in fact they can access reception centers only after their formal registration, which can take place even months after the formal presentation of the asylum application. Therefore, “asylum seekers can face obstacles in finding alternative temporary accommodation solutions, [and those] lacking economic resources are obliged to either resort to friends or to emergency facilities, or to sleep rough” (AIDA 2018: 83). This problem was highlighted already in 2013 in a report by the Chamber of Deputies and Senate of the Republic, where it emerges that “in practice, there are cases of significant expansion of the time period between the submission of the asylum application by the applicant and its formalization by the competent *Questura*. During this period of time, asylum seekers are completely deprived of any form of reception and therefore risk finding themselves in conditions of extreme distress. It is therefore important to guarantee

immediate access to the asylum procedure at the competent *Questura* to anyone who manifests their will, as well as to reduce to a minimum the period of time required for the completion of the procedures” (Chamber of Deputies and Senate of the Republic 2013a: 21).

The above described issue is also partly due to decisions of withdrawal of material reception conditions. As discussed in section 3.3, according to Article 23(1) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 the Prefect can decide to revoke material reception conditions if: (a) the asylum seeker did not present him or herself at the assigned center or left the center without notifying the Prefecture; (b) the asylum seeker did not present him or herself before the competent authorities for the personal interview even though he or she was notified thereof; (c) the asylum seeker has previously lodged an asylum application in Italy; (d) the authorities decide that the asylum seeker possesses sufficient financial resources; or (e) the asylum seeker has committed a serious violation or continuous violation of the accommodation center’s internal rules or the asylum seeker’s conduct was considered seriously violent. As provided by Article 20 of Directive 2013/33/EU, decisions for reduction or, in exceptional and duly justified cases, withdrawal of material reception conditions, shall be taken individually, objectively and impartially. Moreover, decisions shall be based on the particular situation of the person concerned, taking into account the principle of proportionality. Article 23(2) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 in fact states that the Prefect must take into account the specific conditions of vulnerability of asylum seeker. However, as reported by *Médecins Sans Frontières* and AIDA, the decision of withdrawal of reception conditions often is adopted without taking into account the principle of proportionality (AIDA 2018; Medici Senza Frontiere 2018). For example, in the case of withdrawal of material reception conditions for serious violation of the reception center’s internal rules or for violent behavior, AIDA (2018) highlights that the law does not clarify what is meant by ‘serious violations of the reception center’s internal rules and “this has allowed Prefectures to misuse the provision revoking reception measures on ill-founded grounds [...]. [There have been cases in which] Prefectures have interpreted conditions strictly or have considered certain forms of conduct to be ‘serious’ without evaluating them in the context in which they occurred”³¹. This might constitute a violation of Article 20 of Directive 2013/33/EU according to which the withdrawal of reception conditions should be an exceptional measure. Moreover, Article 20 does not solely refer to ‘withdrawal’ but also to reduction. However, Article 23(2) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 does not refer to the fact that reception conditions may be reduced without being withdrawn.

An important aspect that has been highlighted by the meso-level interviewees is the impossibility for asylum seekers to choose their place of residence:

“what the managers of the reception centers have told me is that those who arrive at the center are located by the Prefecture and do not even have geographical awareness” (MEI no. 3); *“there is a strong discretion on arrival, especially on the area of assignment on the territory”* (MEI no. 4); *“it is Department of Civil Liberties and Immigration that decides [...] according to availability”* (MEI no 12).

Overall, the Italian reception system has a capacity of about 180.000 places. As already discussed in section 3.2, asylum seekers should be temporarily accommodated in Extraordinary Reception Center (CAS) identified and activated by the Prefecture only in the event of unavailability of places in first and second reception facilities. However, as shown in

³¹ For example, in several cases the decision to withdraw reception conditions was taken against asylum seekers who participated in protests against the conditions of the reception center where they were accommodated (AIDA 2018: 89).

Figure 6, currently these centers constitute the dominant form of reception in Italy. This reflects the willingness to maintain the system in an emergency perspective (MEI no. 13). By the end of 2018, almost 140.000 asylum seekers were accommodated in CAS (around 9.000 throughout the territory). As stressed by the Chamber of Deputies, the excessive use of extraordinary reception centers is “perhaps the most serious anomaly of our reception system” (Chamber of Deputies 2017: 115).

Figure 6. Reception occupancy in Italy by type of accommodation

Source: AIDA (2019: 22)

This situation is made even more problematic by the changes implemented by Decree Law No. 113/2018, which prevents asylum seekers from accessing second reception facilities – namely the SPRAR, now renamed SIPROIMI. As stressed by a NGO office manager,

“today, with implementation of the Decree, in our cities decisions to withdraw reception conditions have been taken against hundreds of asylum seekers staying in CAS centers [...]. The result will be greater social exclusion and, thus, greater insecurity [for asylum seekers]” (MEI no. 8).

RESPOND roundtable of the Italian Migration Governance Network: Implication of the ‘Salvini Decree’ on reception conditions³²

On the 2nd of July 2019, the second RESPOND roundtable of the Italian Migration Governance Network was held at the University of Florence, eight months after the first one. On that occasion, the purpose was to discuss some key issues relating to governance of the migration phenomenon in Italy. In particular, the discussion revolved around three main migration policy areas: border management, reception, and integration policies. Participants were encouraged to share different points of view and approaches and were free to raise new points for reflection. Specifically, they were asked to focus on the main changes that

³² Extract from the RESPOND blog post by Andrea Terlizzi and Mattia Collini, available at https://www.respondmigration.com/blog-1/roundtable-italian-migration-governance-network#_ftnref

have occurred since 2011 and the most important actors involved in policy formulation and implementation.

This roundtable maintained the same framework. Participants, including lawyers, legal experts, decision makers, social workers, and activists, were asked to focus on two main topics: a) changes occurring after the approval of the so-called “Salvini decree” in October 2018³³ and b) the role of labour market policies in favoring integration processes. The first part was largely a follow-up to the previous event, and aimed to shed light on the practical implications of the new legislation on reception practices, as well as the activities carried out by the Territorial Commissions for the Recognition of International Protection (*Commissioni Territoriali per il Riconoscimento della Protezione Internazionale*). The second topic explored mostly regarded the importance of work and labour oriented policies for a successful social integration of migrants, with a focus on the relevance of civil society associations in orienting migrants and especially in helping them to gain access to the labour market.

In the first part of the discussion, which is the focus of this report, the participants have firstly underlined problems linked to the procedural difficulties for asylum seekers in obtaining the residence in the municipalities where they are hosted. This has effect in terms of the “feelings of belonging” to a community, as one can feel excluded from a local community. Nevertheless, basic services such as healthcare are still provided to asylum seekers who are not registered as residents. Another aspect upon which participants have insisted is that the ‘Salvini decree’ revoked the right of asylum seekers to be hosted in the SPRAR facilities, who are now supposed to find their own accommodation once they leave the CAS. This situation resulted in thousands of people being thrown into the street in a matter of days, increasing problems linked to the accommodation business and the black market. Moreover, more stringent rules for those hosted in the CAS structures – accompanied by a reduction in (per capita) funding – resulted in distrust and demoralization. Asylum seekers residing in these centers do not trust the personnel, not even cultural mediators, who are often considered to be ‘siding with the Italians’, while they are in fact forced to apply and convey regulations that are imposed upon them. The lack of trust is amplified by the unevenness of the whole reception system, with asylum seekers and refugees being treated differently in different centers and localities because of discretionary interpretation of the new rules. This is worsened by the stricter mechanism of checks and controls operated in some areas by the Police and Governmental Authorities (*Questure*³⁴), which results in an increase of the annulment of the right to be hosted in the reception structures, often for minor violations. Overall, the new regulations have the effect of increasing insecurity and deviant behaviors. In fact, asylum seekers and refugees out of the reception system often end up being exploited by criminal networks.

First reception facilities and CAS are often overcrowded, with several deficiencies such as lack of legal advice, remoteness from local communities, difficulties in accessing appropriate information. As for the latter, our interviewees have stressed the problem of the access to clear (legal) information for asylum seekers:

³³ Decree-Law No. 113/2018.

³⁴ The *Questure* are police authorities that mainly deal with public safety and security.

“the need to have access to clear information is enormous [...]. It is already difficult for an Italian operator who goes to ask for information on behalf of an asylum seeker. Very often there are no mediators” (MEI no. 6).

Moreover, problems linked to a lack of hygiene and safety conditions for both guests and staff – as well as a lack of preparation of the staff and staff shortages – have been highlighted. With regard to the staff in particular, it has also been pointed out that

“there is a big problem with operators because there is no defined legislation in this area. The fact that there is no clear and recognized role greatly limits the work because the role is not well defined [...]. I know that in my organization I do everything and I find myself acting as a ‘wild card’. In addition to the role of the social worker, a series of tasks that are not well defined are accumulating [...]. We [operators] are responsible for everything” (MEI no 14).

Material reception conditions vary throughout the country depending on the reception center’s size, occupancy rate, as well as the managing body and the staff (AIDA 2018: 97, 99). This has been highlighted in a report by the Chamber of Deputies, according to which CAS centers are the facilities “that present the greatest problems in terms of quality of services provided, especially in terms of legal information, cultural mediation, social and labor integration, [...] professionalism and specialization of the employees. This also leads to frequent situations of unequal treatment of migrants so that, for the same legal status, they can be received in very different conditions” (Chamber of Deputies 2017: 116). The problem of territorial differentiation has also been stressed by some meso-level interviewees:

“there is no effective system for verifying the performance of these [bodies managing reception centers], which behave differently throughout Italy [...]. There are facilities that work very effectively and facilities where the quality is very low” (MEI no 10);

“there are excellent reception centers and other centers that leave [asylum seekers] without food and heating, without legal advice, without school, and if [asylum seekers] complain, they report them” (MEI no. 9);

“[asylum seekers] must have the good fortune to end up in a well-functioning reception center” (MEI no 1).

According to a recent report by *Médecins Sans Frontières*, at least 10.000 applicants and holders are excluded from the Italian reception system, with limited or no access to essential goods and medical care, and, out of the total number of asylum seekers and refugees, only the 17 % is received within the SPRAR system (Medici Senza Frontiere 2018). Moreover, the presence of applicants/holders of international protections within illegal occupations of buildings, both public and private, has increased. On this regard, it has been stressed the significant role played by social movements claiming the right to housing: “many housing occupations, born as illegal actions, have been regularized afterwards, with the involvement not only of private bodies, but also of institutions, first of all municipalities and regions. [...] The occupations affirm a model based on significant forms of self-management, on the recovery of existing but unused buildings, on the possibility for asylum seekers ‘to remain in reception’ until they achieve effective social, housing and work autonomy” (Medici Senza Frontiere 2018: 8).

As already discussed, the SPRAR system has been deeply reformed, even though it was recognized as a national and European *best practice*. Several strengths of the system have

been highlighted over the years, such as the involvement of municipalities and therefore of local communities in the reception system, the development of an integrated model of reception, the quality of the health, psychological and legal protection that was provided to applicants (Ministry of the Interior 2015a, n.d.). As highlighted in a 2013 report by the Chamber of Deputies and Senate of the Republic, “[the SPRAR system] is widely appreciated in Europe, [since it] is based on interinstitutional cooperation between the State and local authorities, with the collaborative contribution of civil society. In the structures belonging to the SPRAR network, in addition to the services normally provided in government centers for immigrants, integration courses are carried out which include the teaching of the Italian language, orientation to the territory and professional training. There are also some specific projects aimed at the so-called vulnerable categories, which also include minors. The system appears well designed, but suffers from a structural inadequacy of the available resources” (Chamber of Deputies and Senate of the Republic 2013: 10). As also stressed in another report, “[the SPRAR receives] largely positive opinions, with the exception of the [...] insufficient material capacity of the system, especially as a result of the exceptional migration flows of 2011: to date [2012], in fact, the system provides only 3,000 places, which are insufficient compared to the number of asylum seekers and refugees in Italy” (Chamber of Deputies and Senate of the Republic 2013a: 22). The capacity of the SPRAR system has increased over time, from 3.000 places of 2012 to about 31.000 places in 2012 (Chamber of Deputies 2017).

As documented in a report by the Chamber of Deputies in 2017, there is “a marked divergence between the abstract model of the reception system normatively outlined by Legislative Decree No. 142 of 2015 and its practical implementation” (Chamber of Deputies 2017: 115). For example, it has been highlighted “the lack of ‘fluidity’ in the transition from first to second reception facilities, that is mainly due to the lack of places in the SPRAR system. The lack of necessary turn over, together with the exponential increase in the arrivals of migrants in the last four years, determines the saturation and excessive permanence of migrants in first reception facilities” (Chamber of Deputies 2017: 115).

The asylum seekers we have interviewed did not raise any crucial issue regarding the general reception conditions. However, as already pointed out in section 2, almost all of the interviews were conducted in reception centers and this might have affected the interviewees’ responses. For example, they might not have felt free to talk about the reception conditions of the centers. Some interviewees have expressed concerns about the difficulties in finding a job: *“I don’t like seeing me doing nothing!”* (MII no. 16). Almost all of them agreed that the primary barrier to the access to the labor market is the lack of the necessary documents and the language:

“Well... If you don’t have documents it is difficult to find a job!” (MII no. 2); *“I’m not working. I’m looking for a job but I can’t without documents!”* (MII no. 8); *“I don’t work. I submitted my curriculum though. The problem are the documents and the language* (MII no. 20); *“I know that immigrants need documents to work...”* (MII no. 22).

Early access to Labor market and education

Though Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, provides that the residence permit issued to asylum seekers allows the latter to start to work within 60 days from the registration of the asylum application (Art. 22 (1)), in practice asylum seeker face many obstacles in obtaining the residence permit and therefore in accessing the labor market. The primary difficulty lies in the delay in the formal registration of the asylum application, which is necessary in order to obtain

the permit (AIDA 2018). Decree Law No. 113/2018, which abolished the possibility for asylum seekers to enter the SPRAR system, had several implications on the possibility of asylum seekers to access the labor market. In fact, as discussed in section 3.3, the integrated reception services provided by second reception facilities through the SPRAR (now SIPROIMI) system include vocational training and job assistance. The Decree *de facto* prevents asylum seekers to benefit from these services.

As for access to education, the Consolidated Law on Immigration provides that “foreign minors present on the territory are subject to compulsory schooling, [and] all the provisions in force regarding the right to education, access to educational services and participation in the life of the school community apply to them” (Art. 38(1)). Moreover, according to Presidential Decree No. 394/1999³⁵, “foreign minors present on the national territory have the right to education regardless of the regularity of their position with regard to their stay, in the forms and manner provided for Italian citizens” (Art. 45(1)). However, as highlighted by AIDA (2018) in practice, there are several difficulties linked to the reluctance of some schools to enroll foreign students, the unavailability of places and the difficulty to reach the schools if the centers are placed in remote areas.

Within our micro-level interview sample, most interviewees have attended (or were attending) Italian language classes as well as secondary school:

“I participated to many integration activities, I did many exams, I got a B2 language certificate as well as the secondary school diploma (MII no. 29). The importance of education has been stressed in several occasions: “to live in a new country you have to learn about its culture first. Now I’m attending secondary school and that’s fine” (MII no. 19).

Services and allowances

Asylum seekers in reception centers, including CAS, receives 2.50 € per day as pocket money for personal needs. Decree Law No. 113/2018 has reduced the daily amount per person allocated to the bodies managing reception centers from 35 € to 21 €. According to AIDA (2018: 85) this might have forced “contractors to opt for large centers, reducing the number of operators and the activities offered in the centers”. Moreover, activities such as teaching Italian language, orientation to local services, professional training, psychological support as well as leisure activities are no longer covered. Our meso-level interviewees have particularly stressed the importance of teaching Italian language:

“the primary need is an adequate learning of the Italian language because the language is the main instrument of integration in a country. [...] Many times adequate standards are not guaranteed” (MEI no. 4).

According to Article 36 of the Consolidated Law on Immigration, irregular migrants have the right to access emergency outpatient and hospital as well as preventive medicine programs aimed at safeguarding individual and public health. Asylum seekers acquire the right to health care assistance at the moment they register their asylum application. However, this very much depends on the attribution of the tax code assigned by the *Questure*, which might

³⁵ Presidential Decree No 394 of 31 August 1999, “*Regolamento recante norme di attuazione del testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell’immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero, a norma dell’articolo 1, comma 6, del decreto legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286*”.

be delayed – in some regions, even for several months (AIDA 2018). As provided by Presidential Decree No. 394/1999, the right to health care assistance does not expire during the renewal phase of the residence permit. In practice, however, due to bureaucratic delays asylum seekers with an expired permit of stay might have no guarantee of access to non-urgent medical treatments for a significant length of time (AIDA 2018). Moreover, it should not be underestimated the language barrier as possible obstacle to access health care services. In fact, “usually medical operators only speak Italian and there are no cultural mediators or interpreters who could facilitate the mutual understanding between operator and patient. Therefore asylum seekers and refugees often do not address their general doctor and go to the hospital only when their disease gets worse” (AIDA 2018: 105).

Reception of Vulnerable Groups

As discussed in section 3.4, Article 17(1) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015 provides that reception conditions have to take into account ‘the specific needs of vulnerable persons, such as minors, unaccompanied minors, disabled persons, elderly people, pregnant women, single parents with minor children, victims of human trafficking, persons suffering from serious illness or mental disorders, victims of genital mutilation, persons who have been subjected to torture, rape or other serious forms of psychological, physical or sexual violence, as well as victims of violence related to sexual orientation or gender identity’. However, as highlighted by AIDA (2018: 107), “there are no legal provisions on how, when and by whom this assessment should be carried out”. Though according to Article 9(4) of the Decree the assessment of the presence of vulnerable asylum seekers with special reception needs is undertaken since they enter first reception centers, in practice the reduction of funding and services undermines the effective identification and protection of vulnerable people (AIDA 2018).

As for the concept of vulnerability, a legal expert has stressed the issue that the vulnerability itself is often hidden:

“while there are obvious objective and verifiable aspects such as in the case children and the elderly, the victim of trafficking or torture, for example, is not revealed at first glance. Consequently, the quality of the reception service and the ability of the operators to identify and identify particular vulnerabilities is important, which has a decisive impact on the individual path of that person. Therefore, there is a need for greater training of operators working in reception centers on vulnerability and the development of coordination mechanisms with specialized services [...]. It is important to be properly trained to identify vulnerability and report it to the appropriate service. This is a procedure that should be done from the moment of disembarkation to identify the most appropriate form of reception or even to secure people who arrive in situations of poor security, such as victims of trafficking. The possibility of early identification is provided by international legislation and has been poorly implemented by Italy” (MEI no 13).

Though the reception centers should ensure the protection of family unity (Art. 10(1) of Legislative Decree No. 142/2015), in practice “it may happen that a father is accommodated in a wing for single men and his wife and children in the wing for women, [and] that the parents are divided and placed in different centers, and usually the children are accommodated with the mother” (AIDA 2018: 107). Moreover, no specific mechanism is put in place to prevent gender-based violence in reception centers.

Unaccompanied foreign minors

As for unaccompanied children, they have access to the newly created SIPROIMI (former SPRAR) system. However, AIDA (2018) reports that the number of places dedicated to unaccompanied children still falls short of current needs. It is important to remark that, in 2014, the European Commission sent the Italian government a letter opening an infringement procedure (procedure n. 2014/2171) regarding the protection of unaccompanied foreign minors seeking asylum, claiming the violation of obligations required under EU law (Ministry of the Interior 2015a). Though the Commission acknowledged that Italian legislation provides an adequate legislative framework aimed at guaranteeing a high level of protection to unaccompanied minors, it also highlighted that, in practice, access to the asylum procedures for unaccompanied minors was often delayed due to the long waiting times for the appointment of the tutors. In many cases “the same tutor is appointed for a large number of minors, with negative repercussions on the possibility of establishing a relation-ship of trust” (Ministry of the Interior 2015a: 41). Moreover, the Commission stressed that here is no legal provision stating that the legal tutors must be trained and must have specific skills. At the level of formal legal framework, these last criticisms have been overcome with Legislative Decree No. 142/2015, which specifies that qualified personnel are required to have an interview with the minor, aimed at bringing out any element useful for his or her protection. These activities have to be undertaken together with a cultural mediator and assisted, where possible, by organizations with proven and specific experience in the protection of minors.

5. Conclusion: Challenges, prospects, and policy recommendations

The aim of this report has been to investigate the Italian reception regime and its developments from 2011 to 2018. Empirical material has been drawn from documents, semi-structured interviews, secondary sources, and academic literature. The report has firstly reviewed the formal legal and policy framework, describing the functioning of the reception system along the phases of first aid and assistance, first reception, and second reception. It has been shown that the system is formally based on a loyal cooperation between national, regional, and municipal levels of government, involving different actors at all levels of government.

The report has then scrutinized the discrepancy between the norms and the actual functioning of the reception system. In fact, it has been reported that what is formally guaranteed to asylum seekers by law is not fully implemented in practice. Several key issues have been highlighted. It has been stressed that, though the regional level formally enjoy responsibility, in practice this level of government is bypassed. It has also been highlighted the crucial role played by civil society associations vis-à-vis institutional actors and the insufficient level of collaboration between state and non-state actors.

As for first aid and assistance, the ‘hotspot approach’ suffers from many deficiencies. The activities taking place in hotspots lack a clear and solid legal basis. In fact, hotspots are not regulated by any EU directive or regulation nor by primary Italian legislation, as they are provided for and disciplined by secondary legislation. Moreover, several criticalities have been reported by non-governmental actors. Concerns have been related to the identification procedure, with migrants who have been often classified as asylum seekers or economic migrants depending on a summary assessment. Poor living conditions and severe violations of fundamental rights in hotspots as well as in pre-removal facilities have also been detected.

With regard to first and second reception, there are problems concerning the time period between the submission of the asylum application by the applicant and its formalization by the authorities. In fact, though formally asylum seekers have the right to material reception conditions immediately after claiming asylum, they in fact can access them only after the formal registration of the application, which can take place many months after the submission of the asylum application. Moreover, issues concerning decisions to withdraw material reception conditions without taking into account the principle of proportionality have been stressed. Other problematic aspects are constituted by territorial differences in reception practices and discretionary interpretation of the rules (by both the authorities and management bodies of reception centers), the excessive use of extraordinary reception centers, the access to clear (legal) information for asylum seekers, as well as to health services (including psychological support), housing, labour market and education system. Finally, problems raised by the approval of Decree-Law No. 113/2018 (the so-called ‘Salvini Decree’) have been particularly stressed. The ‘Salvini decree’ revoked the right of asylum seekers to be hosted in the SPRAR facilities, who are now supposed to find their own accommodation once they leave first reception facilities and CAS. This situation resulted in thousands of people being thrown into the street in a matter of days, increasing problems linked to the accommodation business and the black market. This has resulted in increasing insecurity for asylum seekers and deviant behaviors. In fact, asylum seekers and refugees out of the reception system often end up being exploited by criminal networks.

Policy recommendations

Overall, in light of these issues, the main policy recommendations are as follows:

1. Increase the role of the regional level as an interlocutor between the central government and the municipalities in order to improve coordination in multi-level governance.
2. Strengthen cooperation between civil society associations and institutional actors, with the latter that should better support non-state actors and favor the establishment of networks between them.
3. Strengthen activities of psychological support for migrants, asylum seekers, and refugees both in places of disembarkation (hotspots) and in first and second reception facilities.
4. Speed-up decision making and administrative procedures so that to guarantee immediate access to material reception conditions, as well as to health services, housing, labour market, and education system.
5. Applying the principles of proportionality and exceptionality when taking decisions over the reduction or withdrawal of material reception conditions.
6. Limit the use of extraordinary reception centers (CAS) and restore and strengthen the SPRAR system.
7. Set up a system to monitor and verify the performance of the bodies managing reception centers and guarantee territorial uniformity in access to material reception conditions throughout the country.

Appendices

EU legislation

Directive 2013/33/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 laying down standards for the reception of applicants for international protection (recast)

Directive 2013/32/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 26 June 2013 on common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection

Regulation (EU) No 516/2014 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 16 April 2014 establishing the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, amending Council Decision 2008/381/EC and repealing Decisions No 573/2007/EC and No 575/2007/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and Council Decision 2007/435/EC

Council Directive 2003/9/EC of 27 January 2003 laying down minimum standards for the reception of asylum seekers

National legislation

Law No 184 of 4 May 1983, *“Disciplina dell'adozione e dell'affidamento dei minori”*.

Law No 563 of 29 December 1995, *“Conversione in legge del decreto-legge 30 ottobre 1995, n. 451, recante disposizioni urgenti per l'ulteriore impiego del personale delle Forze armate in attivita' di controllo della frontiera marittima nella regione Puglia”*

Legislative Decree No 286 of 25 July 1998, *“Testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero”*.

Presidential Decree No 394 of 31 August 1999, *“Regolamento recante norme di attuazione del testo unico delle disposizioni concernenti la disciplina dell'immigrazione e norme sulla condizione dello straniero, a norma dell'articolo 1, comma 6, del decreto legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286”*.

Prime Ministerial Decree of 9 December 1999, *“Regolamento concernente i compiti del Comitato per i minori stranieri, a norma dell'articolo 33, commi 2 e 2-bis, del decreto legislativo 25 luglio 1998, n. 286”*.

Law No 189 of 30 July 2002, *“Modifica alla normativa in materia di immigrazione e di asilo”*

Legislative Decree No 140 of 30 May 2005, *“Attuazione della direttiva 2003/9/CE che stabilisce norme minime relative all'accoglienza dei richiedenti asilo negli Stati membri”*

Legislative Decree No 142 of 18 August 2015, *“Attuazione della direttiva 2013/33/UE recante norme relative all'accoglienza dei richiedenti protezione internazionale, nonche' della direttiva 2013/32/UE, recante procedure comuni ai fini del riconoscimento e della revoca dello status di protezione internazionale”*

Ministerial Decree of 10 August 2016, *“Modalita' di accesso da parte degli enti locali ai finanziamenti del Fondo nazionale per le politiche ed i servizi dell'asilo per la predisposizione dei servizi di accoglienza per i richiedenti e i beneficiari di protezione internazionale e per i titolari del permesso umanitario, nonche' approvazione delle*

linee guida per il funzionamento del Sistema di protezione per richiedenti asilo e rifugiati (SPRAR)”

Circular of the Ministry of the Interior of 11 October 2016, “*Regole per l'avvio di un sistema di ripartizione graduale e sostenibile dei richiedenti asilo e dei rifugiati sul territorio nazionale attraverso lo SPRAR*”.

Legislative Decree No 13 of 17 February 2017, “*Disposizioni urgenti per l'accelerazione dei procedimenti in materia di protezione internazionale, nonché per il contrasto dell'immigrazione illegale*”.

Law No 47 of 7 April 2017, “*Disposizioni in materia di misure di protezione dei minori stranieri non accompagnati*”.

Decree Law No 113 of 4 October 2018, “*Disposizioni urgenti in materia di protezione internazionale e immigrazione, sicurezza pubblica, nonché misure per la funzionalità del Ministero dell'interno e l'organizzazione e il funzionamento dell'Agenzia nazionale per l'amministrazione e la destinazione dei beni sequestrati e confiscati alla criminalità organizzata*”

Law No 132 of 1 December 2018, “*Conversione in legge, con modificazioni, del decreto-legge 4 ottobre 2018, n. 113, recante disposizioni urgenti in materia di protezione internazionale e immigrazione, sicurezza pubblica, nonché misure per la funzionalità del Ministero dell'interno e l'organizzazione e il funzionamento dell'Agenzia nazionale per l'amministrazione e la destinazione dei beni sequestrati e confiscati alla criminalità organizzata. Delega al Governo in materia di riordino dei ruoli e delle carriere del personale delle Forze di polizia e delle Forze armate*”

List of meso level interviews (MEI)

Interview number	Organization	Role
1	Legal association	Legal expert
2	Intercultural association	Activist
3	Legal association	Legal expert
4	Research institute	Migration expert
5	University	Migration expert
6	NGO	Office manager
7	Social cooperative	Social worker
8	NGO	Office manager
9	Social and artist collective	Activist
10	University and Territorial Commission	Migration expert
11	Reception center	Manager
12	Law enforcement	Decision-maker
13	Legal association	Legal expert
14	Social cooperative	Social worker
15	Ministry of the Interior	Official

List of micro level interviews (MII)

Interview number	Nationality	Age	Status
MII_1	Gambia (Man)	Not applicable	Asylum seeker
MII_2	Gambia (Man)	22	Asylum seeker
MII_3	Gambia (Man)	24	Asylum seeker
MII_4	Gambia (Man)	18	Asylum seeker
MII_5	Camerun (Man)	31	Asylum seeker
MII_6	Nigeria (Man)	26	Asylum seeker
MII_7	Nigeria (Man)	21	Asylum seeker
MII_8	Nigeria (Man)	20	Asylum seeker
MII_9	Ghana (Man)	24	Asylum seeker
MII_10	Nigeria (Man)	31	Asylum seeker
MII_11	Nigeria (Man)	28	Asylum seeker
MII_12	Ghana (Man)	28	Asylum seeker
MII_13	Sierra Leone (Man)	22	Asylum seeker
MII_14	Ivory Coast (Man)	23	Special protection
MII_15	Morocco (Man)	27	Asylum seeker
MII_16	Liberia (Man)	24	Asylum seeker
MII_17	Libya (Man)	22	Asylum seeker
MII_18	Pakistan (Man)	24	Asylum seeker
MII_19	Ghana (Man)	26	Asylum seeker
MII_20	Nigeria (Woman)	27	Asylum seeker
MII_21	Nigeria (Woman)	24	Asylum seeker
MII_22	Nigeria (Woman)	25	Refugee
MII_23	El Salvador (Man)	37	Migrant
MII_24	Senegal (Man)	36	Migrant
MII_25	Gambia (Man)	26	Subsidiary protection
MII_26	Mali (Man)	29	Humanitarian protection
MII_27	Nigeria (Man)	32	Humanitarian protection
MII_28	Nigeria (Man)	55	Migrant
MII_29	Ivory Coast (Man)	26	Humanitarian protection

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